

Tumor-LN-oC / End-users Questionnaire.

Data generated according to the responses until M18 (end of Oct 2022) of the project.

Role - Field of expertise

31 responses

Country

31 responses

Which cancer types are you interested in?

31 responses

Metastatic potential

30 responses

Metastasis promoting cytokines/chemokines

28 responses

Surface markers associated with metastasis

29 responses

Immune cell infiltration/inflammation

28 responses

Differentiation

27 responses

Tumor margins

22 responses

Do you want to detect more than one feature simultaneously?

31 responses

Which sample type do you want to analyze?

30 responses

You are interested in:

30 responses

How many specimens do you want to test per week?

30 responses

What analysis duration do you expect?

31 responses

How many specimens do you want to test simultaneously?

31 responses

How many preparation steps (tissue collection, processing, analysis etc.) you perform in your work for a standard analysis?

25 responses

How much time do you spend for sample preparation before the analysis?

26 responses

What is the specimen dimension for examination?

25 responses

Do you think that an automated system is:

31 responses

What steps would need to be automated?

31 responses

What system dimensions do you prefer?

31 responses

What system weight you accept?

30 responses

What connectivity would you prefer?

31 responses

What is the cost per sample analysis you can accept?

31 responses

Would the end-user prefer reusable chips or disposable ones?

31 responses

Which price are you willing to pay for the OoC platform?

30 responses

Which price are you willing to pay for the OoC platform?

30 responses

What is the qualification level of the operator to use the instrument?

26 responses

What level of user experience do you expect?

31 responses

What kind of result do you prefer?

23 responses

